

MENTAL SKILL AND SELF EFFICACY OF UNIVERSITY VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS (Male): A STUDY OF KERALA STATE

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Abstract:

The present study was investigated to know the difference between mental skill and self- efficacy among university level men's volleyball players of Kerala. In this study, the researcher was used as a survey method in online form. 48 samples were selected from 4 universities of Kerala. From the total of 48 subjects, the subjects were further delimited to 12 subjects from each university. The subject ranged from 17 to 25 years. The Bull, Albison and Shambrook (1996) mental skill questionnaire was used to measure the mental skill among the volleyball players and Bandura (1997) self-efficacy questionnaire was used to measure the self-efficacy among the volleyball players which were standardized questionnaire and also considered for reliability.

Considering the Anova of mental skills among various universities $F(3, 44) > 2.76, p = .05$, only one variable is significantly different with $F(3, 44) = 5.669, p = .002$ is concentration ability and all the other variables shows no significant differences among various universities. It shows that Kannur University is significantly different than Calicut and MG University whereas there is no significant difference in concentration ability between Kannur and Kerala University. It shows that Kerala University is significantly different than Calicut and MG University whereas there is no significant difference in concentration ability between Kannur and Kerala University. There is no significant difference in concentration ability between Calicut University and MG University. Considering the Anova on self-efficacy among various universities $F(3, 44) > 2.76, p = .05$, only one variable is significantly different with $F(3, 44) = 4.089, p = .012$ is Academic self-efficacy, and all the other variables shows no significant differences among various universities. Post hoc was done to find out the difference on various universities. It shows that Kannur University is significantly different on Academic self-efficacy among the Calicut and Kerala universities whereas there is no significant difference to MG University. MG University shows no significant difference to all other universities in Academic self-efficacy.

Key Words: Mental Skill, Volleyball, Self-Efficacy

Introduction:

Sports psychology deals with aspects of behavior and with the feelings, thoughts and motivations underlying that behavior. It is an important subject to academically useful aspects along with research and professional significance. Psychology is an applied field of science and it is used to study behavioral pattern of players in sports at different competitive levels. It has become a major discipline recently, and lots of academicians and researchers are working in this field. Sports psychology is a branch to study of sports men's behavior scientifically in various sport settings. Sports are typically understood as recreational activity, physical activities as well as highly organized competitive athletics events and games such as Volleyball and Basketball etc.

Mental Skill:

Mental skills training is the process that provides the methods and techniques to improve performance by developing self-confidence and creating a positive mind-set through goal setting, positive self-talk, visualization, imagery, and self-efficacy.

Self-Efficacy:

Self-efficacy is the belief in ones effectiveness in performing specific tasks. People, who regard themselves as highly efficacious act, think and feel differently from those who perceive themselves as inefficacious.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the level of mental skill and self-efficacy among university level volleyball players of Kerala.
- To compare the level of mental skill and self -efficacy among university level volleyball players of Kerala.

Methodology:

The study consists of 48 university level men's volleyball players selected from 4 universities in Kerala state (university of Calicut, university of Kannur, university of MG and university of Kerala) of age ranged from

17 to 25 years. The One-Way ANOVA procedure produces a one-way analysis of variance for a quantitative dependent variable by a single factor (independent) variable. Analysis of variance is used to test the hypothesis that several means are equal. This technique is an extension of the two-sample t test.

Simple Bar Mean of Mental skills by University

Simple Bar Mean of Self efficacy by University

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Anova on Mental Skills among Various Universities

	Sum of Squares		df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Imagery Ability	Between Groups	10.229	3	3.41	0.437	0.728
	Within Groups	343.25	44	7.801		
	Total	353.479	47			
Mental Preparation	Between Groups	9.729	3	3.243	1.059	0.376
	Within Groups	134.75	44	3.063		
	Total	144.479	47			
Self Confidence	Between Groups	15.896	3	5.299	1.359	0.268
	Within Groups	171.583	44	3.9		
	Total	187.479	47			

Anxiety and Worry Management	Between Groups	5.562	3	1.854	0.231	0.874
	Within Groups	352.417	44	8.009		
	Total	357.979	47			
Concentration ability	Between Groups	91.417	3	30.472	5.669	.002*
	Within Groups	236.5	44	5.375		
	Total	327.917	47			
Relaxation Ability	Between Groups	17.896	3	5.965	0.837	0.481
	Within Groups	313.583	44	7.127		
	Total	331.479	47			
Motivation	Between Groups	14.5	3	4.833	0.928	0.435
	Within Groups	229.167	44	5.208		
	Total	243.667	47			

Considering the Anova of mental skills among various universities $F(3,44) > 2.76$, $p = .05$, only one variable is significantly different with $F(3,44) = 5.669$, $p = .002$ is Concentration ability, and all the other variables shows no significant differences among various universities. Post hoc was done to find out the difference on various universities.

Table 1.1: Posthoc Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable	(I) University	(J) University	Mean	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
			Difference e(I-J)			Lower Bound	Upper Bound

Concentration Ability	Calicut University	University of Kerala	-2.583*	0.946	0.043	-5.11	-0.06
		MG University	0	0.946	1	-2.53	2.53
		Kannur University	-2.917*	0.946	0.018	-5.44	-0.39
	University of Kerala	Calicut University	2.583*	0.946	0.043	0.06	5.11
		MG University	2.583*	0.946	0.043	0.06	5.11
		Kannur University	-0.333	0.946	0.985	-2.86	2.19
	MG University	Calicut University	0	0.946	1	-2.53	2.53
		University of Kerala	-2.583*	0.946	0.043	-5.11	-0.06
		Kannur University	-2.917*	0.946	0.018	-5.44	-0.39
	Kannur University	Calicut University	2.917*	0.946	0.018	0.39	5.44
		University of Kerala	0.333	0.946	0.985	-2.19	2.86
		MG University	2.917*	0.946	0.018	0.39	5.44

It shows that Kannur University is significantly different than Calicut and MG University whereas there is no significant difference in concentration ability between Kannur and Kerala University. It shows that Kerala University is significantly different than Calicut and MG University whereas there is no significant difference in concentration ability between Kannur and Kerala University. There is no significant difference in concentration ability between Calicut University and MG University.

Table 1.2: Anova on Self-Efficacy among Various Universities

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Academic Self Efficacy	Between Groups	298.896	3	99.632	4.089	.012*
	Within Groups	1072.08	44	24.366		
	Total	1370.98	47			
Social Self Efficacy	Between Groups	37.729	3	12.576	0.508	0.679
	Within Groups	1088.75	44	24.744		
	Total	1126.48	47			
Emotional Self Efficacy	Between Groups	166.5	3	55.5	2.151	0.107
	Within Groups	1135.5	44	25.807		
	Total	1302	47			

Considering the Anova on self-efficacy among various universities $F(3,44) > 2.76$, $p = .05$, only one variable is significantly different with $F(3,44) = 4.089$, $p = .012$ is Academic self-efficacy, and all the other variables shows no significant differences among various universities. Post hoc was done to find out the difference on various universities.

Table 1.3: Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable	(I) University	(J) University	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Academic Self Efficacy	Calicut University	University of Kerala	0.417	2.015	0.997	-4.96	5.8
		MG University	1.417	2.015	0.895	-3.96	6.8
		Kannur University	6.250*	2.015	0.017	0.87	11.63
	University of Kerala	Calicut University	-0.417	2.015	0.997	-5.8	4.96
		MG University	1	2.015	0.96	-4.38	6.38
		Kannur University	5.833*	2.015	0.029	0.45	11.21
	MG University	Calicut University	-1.417	2.015	0.895	-6.8	3.96
		University of Kerala	-1	2.015	0.96	-6.38	4.38
		Kannur University	4.833	2.015	0.092	-0.55	10.21
	Kannur University	Calicut University	-6.250*	2.015	0.017	-11.63	-0.87
		University of Kerala	-5.833*	2.015	0.029	-11.21	-0.45
		MG University	-4.833	2.015	0.092	-10.21	0.55
University of Kerala		-4.833	2.015	0.092	-10.21	0.55	

It shows that Kannur University is significantly different on Academic self-efficacy among the Calicut and Kerala universities whereas there is no significant difference to MG University. MG University shows no significant difference to all other universities in Academic self- efficacy.

Result:

The One-way ANOVA study and its result take us to the following conclusion. The comparison of mental skill and self-efficacy among resulted in finding out the fact that there is a difference in the above mentioned psychological variable of Calicut University, Kannur University, MG University and Kannur University volleyball players were as descriptive statistics brings out that there also some difference between University level volleyball players in the psychological variables like mental skill and self-efficacy.

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